

IMPACT OF INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL ON THE CORPORATE PERFORMANCE OF LISTED AGRICULTURAL FIRMS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: The study evaluated how listed agricultural companies in Nigeria fared financially as a function of their intellectual capital. Examining the impact of capital employed efficiency, structural capital efficiency, and human capital efficiency on return on assets of listed agricultural companies in Nigeria was the specific goal. The study design used in the research is ex post facto. The five (5) listed agricultural enterprises on the Nigerian Exchange Group make up the study's population. The study used secondary data from 2013 to 2022 that was obtained from the selected companies' audited annual reports and accounts. The pooled Ordinary Least Squares approach was used to analyze the data and evaluate the hypotheses. The results showed that listed agricultural enterprises in Nigeria had a positively significant return on equity when their human capital was efficient. Capital employed efficiency has a positive considerable impact on the return on equity of listed agricultural enterprises in Nigeria, while structural capital efficiency has a negative but negligible effect. It was suggested that agricultural companies think about making calculated investments in staff training and development with the goal of raising total output and, as a result, raising financial performance.

Keywords: Human capital efficiency, Structural capital efficiency and Capital employed efficiency and return on equity.

Introduction

There has been a notable shift in the business landscape in recent years, with companies increasingly acknowledging the pivotal role that intellectual capital plays in determining their success. Traditionally, the focus had been primarily on tangible assets, such as physical infrastructure and financial resources (Olohunlana, Odeleye & Isola, 2023; Awwad & Qtaishat, 2023). However, as the business environment evolves and becomes more knowledge-driven, the value of intangible assets, essentially intellectual capital, has become increasingly apparent. Intellectual capital encompasses a broad spectrum of intangible resources, including the expertise and skills of employees, proprietary knowledge, innovative ideas, brand reputation, customer relationships, and organizational culture (Gidado, Adedeji & Ali, 2023; Rufus, Festus & Dada, 2022). These intangible assets collectively add to the competitive advantage of an organization and its market differentiation. Recognizing the significance of intellectual capital, forward-thinking businesses have started placing greater emphasis on

nurturing and leveraging these intangible resources to drive growth, innovation, and profitability (Otuya, Akpoyibo & Edike, 2023). The contribution of intellectual capital to competitiveness has garnered significant attention due to technological advancements, globalization, and the rise of knowledge-base economies (Abba, Hamidu, Kakanda, & Hanga, 2023). Intellectual capital has often been recognised as a crucial factor influencing the productivity and strategic competitiveness of firms. Intellectual capital refers to a collection of intellectual material, knowledge, experience, property, and information that contributes to creating value within an organization (Putri, Budiyanto, Triyonowati & Ilham, 2023; Uagbale-Ekatak & Ofurum, 2022). It represents the wealth of knowledge that a company utilizes in its business operations to generate value. Studies have established that intellectual capital is an intangible asset that can influence a firm's earnings potential and absorptive capacity, making it increasingly regarded as a paramount resource for organizations (Ashraf, Sadiq, Ferreira & Almeida, 2023). In Nigeria, the recognition of intellectual capital's importance is evident in many annual reports and accounts, where the phrase "our greatest assets are our people" frequently appears (Major & Biragbara, 2023). This growing acknowledgment of intellectual capital is based on the belief that people hold as much value as other organizational resources. Over the years, the significance of intellectual capital has significantly increased, and it is now considered a crucial tool for achieving sustainable competitive advantage (Edet, Ebe, Udontah & Umoren, 2023). People are the most influential factor in value creation, as tangible assets can only add value when human beings effectively utilize them. Intellectual capital's dominance is a characteristic of emerging economies driven by global competition; and the valuation of intellectual capital within organizations should be based on its performance, further emphasizing its critical role in organizational success (Habib & Dalwai, 2023). The assessment of intellectual capital efficiency involves determining whether the efforts made in developing intellectual capital contribute to achieving objectives or improving specific outcomes, such as reducing worker absences and turnover, enhancing work efficiency, and increasing productivity (Nguyen, 2023; Chukwuekwu, 2023). At the organizational level, efficiency evaluation provides insights into the company's ability to generate profits from its available resources and ensure future liquidity. This efficiency results from optimizing time, labor, and process costs (Salman, 2023). The effective utilization of human resources plays a crucial role in determining an organization's strength, with intellectual capital efficiency revolving around maximizing productivity from human assets while minimizing costs (Tonye & Oruh, 2022).

In the knowledge-based economy, where information and ideas hold immense power, intellectual capital serves as a critical driver of corporate performance (Abuaddous, Albqour & Salameh, 2023). Companies that effectively harness their employees' expertise, foster a culture of learning and knowledge sharing, and invest in research and development are better positioned to thrive in dynamic and competitive markets. Intellectual capital also plays a vital role in enhancing decision-making processes, enabling companies to make strategic choices backed by valuable insights and informed analyses (Edet, Ebe, Udontah & Umoren, 2023). As the business world becomes increasingly interconnected and digitalized, intellectual capital has emerged as a key differentiator, allowing companies to innovate, adapt, and stay relevant amidst rapid technological

advancements and evolving customer preferences. In this context, the effective management and utilization of intellectual capital have become imperative for sustained success and resilience in a rapidly changing business landscape.

Therefore, the growing recognition of the significance of intellectual capital reflects a paradigm shift in how businesses perceive and leverage their assets. By appreciating the inherent value of knowledge, expertise, and intangible resources, companies are better equipped to optimize their corporate performance, achieve competitive advantage, and build a solid foundation for long-term growth and prosperity. As organizations continue to navigate the complexities of the modern business environment, the effective management and harnessing of intellectual capital will remain central to unlocking new opportunities and driving success in the ever-evolving corporate landscape (Misdar, 2023). A failure to fully harness intellectual capital might lead to reduced innovation, decreased productivity, and inefficient decision-making processes. Additionally, these organizations might struggle to attract and retain top talent, as employees may seek opportunities in firms that prioritize and invest in their professional development (Ashraf, Sadiq, Ferreira & Almeida, 2023). Ultimately, the limited integration of intellectual capital into corporate strategies could hinder the overall performance of Nigerian firms, impacting their ability to thrive in the dynamic and competitive business environment. Existing studies in Nigeria have not included the evidence from 2022 accounting period with respect to agricultural sector of the Nigerian Exchange Group. Besides, there is a sectorial gap, none of the prior studies carried out research on this nature using agricultural sector in Nigeria. This study addresses this gap in literature; the study consequently, determines the effect of intellectual capital on the corporate performance of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are as follows:

- To examine the effect of human capital efficiency on return on equity of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria.
- To ascertain the effect of structural capital efficiency on return on equity of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria.
- To determine the effect of capital employed efficiency on return on equity of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Intellectual Capital

The initial definition of intellectual capital is attributed to Thomas Stewart, a pioneer of the concept. In 1991, in an article titled "Brain Power - How Intellectual Capital is Becoming America's Most Valuable Asset," Stewart defined intellectual capital as the collective knowledge within a company that provides it with a competitive advantage in the market over other firms (Lee & Shek, 2022). This knowledge effectively transforms raw materials and adds value to them. Thus, any knowledge base used for wealth creation is referred to as intellectual capital (Olohunlana, Odeleye & Isola, 2023). The concept of intellectual capital delves into the intangible yet immensely valuable assets that go beyond traditional financial measures (Nguyen, 2023). It encompasses the wealth of knowledge, skills, relationships, and organizational processes that contribute to a company's ability to innovate, compete, and ultimately succeed in the dynamic business landscape

(Chukwuekwu, 2023). At its core, intellectual capital is about leveraging what a company knows and how it operates to create a distinct advantage.

Thomas Stewart's foundational definition captures this essence by highlighting that intellectual capital encompasses the collective wisdom embedded in the minds of a company's employees (Çevik & Arslan, 2022). This knowledge is not limited to facts and figures but extends to insights, best practices, problem-solving approaches, and other intangible assets that can't be easily quantified (Edet, Ebe, Udontah & Umoren, 2023). Intellectual capital encompasses the non-physical sources of added value for a firm, including human capital (such as skills, training, and experience), relational capital (including customer and stakeholder relationships, agreements, and brands), and structural capital (such as company culture, systems, working environment, and intangible rights) (Putri, Budiyanto, Triyonowati & Ilham, 2023).

Intellectual capital encompasses or represents the economic value of human, relational, and structural capital, all of which are intangible assets for a firm (Otuya, Akpoyibo & Edike, 2023). Intellectual capital refers to a complex organizational process involving knowledge management, best practice transfer, and organizational learning. This process transforms employees' skills, knowledge, and expertise into valuable assets crucial for organizational performance. In more specific terms, intellectual capital constitutes the intangible value derived from employee knowledge, skills, business training, and ideas – assets that are not listed in the financial position statement (Chukwuekwu, 2023).

The economic value and success of modern firms rely not only on their manufactured products but also on their intangible assets, which enhance employees' knowledge base for improved productivity and efficiency (Tonye & Oruh, 2022). Intellectual capital encompasses external factors (like brand and reputation) and internal factors (such as skills and competencies), dynamically interlinked intangible assets that enable corporations to leverage tangible assets, financial resources, and human capital to create value (Abba, Hamidu, Kakanda & Hanga, 2023).

Human Capital Efficiency

Human capital efficiency compresses a collection of factors that not only encompass the knowledge and skills possessed by employees but also extend to their intrinsic qualities and how these attributes contribute to the overall functioning of an organization (Major & Biragbara, 2023). Human capital efficiency emphasizes the idea that employees are not just cogs in the machine but rather the driving force behind a company's growth and development (Al-Delawi, Raewf & Jameel, 2023). This intellectual capital category includes not only technical skills but also intangible qualities like creativity, adaptability, and problem-solving abilities (Abba, Hamidu, Kakanda & Hanga, 2023). These attributes contribute to the employees' ability to innovate, find novel solutions, and adapt to changing circumstances – all of which are indispensable in today's fast-paced business environment.

Moreover, human capital efficiency is a multi-dimensional concept that incorporates various aspects of an employee's background and disposition (Salman, 2023). The significance of human capital efficiency within the broader realm of intellectual capital is profound since human capital is not only a component but the linchpin of

intellectual capital (Al-Delawi, Raewf & Jameel, 2023). This assertion is grounded in the understanding that a skilled, motivated, and innovative workforce is the bedrock upon which competitive advantage and groundbreaking innovations are built.

Structural Capital Efficiency

Structural capital efficiency encompasses a diverse spectrum of elements that collectively form the foundation upon which a company's intellectual prowess is built (Salman, 2023). This facet of intellectual capital embraces an array of crucial components – technologies, data repositories, inventive creations, published materials, organizational culture, strategic frameworks, structural setups, and operational systems (Abuaddous, Albqour & Salameh, 2023). In essence, it is the intricate tapestry of procedures, methods, and activities that a company strategically assembles.

The significance of structural capital efficiency goes beyond its mere existence within an organization. It significantly influences the innovation process and directly contributes to the formation of innovative capital – the lifeblood of forward-looking enterprises (Sonali & Kaushala, 2023). The incorporation of advanced technologies and methodologies into operational processes, systems, and structures enhances a company's ability to not only produce goods but also effectively market and distribute them.

Structural capital efficiency comprises the efficiency of vital organizational processes, the accessibility and management of data through databases, the safeguarding of trademarks, the functionality of information systems, and even the intangible aspects of corporate culture (Abba, Hamidu, Kakanda & Hanga, 2023). In simpler terms, structural capital encapsulates the legacy that remains embedded within a company even when the workforce departs at the end of the day.

Capital Employed Efficiency

Capital employed refers to the comprehensive sum of resources strategically deployed within a firm's fixed and current assets (Tonye & Oruh, 2022). It encompasses the amalgamation of equity capital and noncurrent liabilities – a composite of funding sources that sustains the company's operations. In simpler terms, capital employed encapsulates the aggregate value of fixed assets and working capital. However, the mere presence of capital employed doesn't tell the full story – it's the efficiency with which these resources are utilized that truly matters. Capital employed efficiency entails all the intricacies of resource utilization within a firm's production and business activities (Sonali & Kaushala, 2023).

Capital employed efficiency emerges as a strategic avenue for this optimization. It's akin to a performance metric that gauges the organization's ability to convert financial inputs into valuable outputs. This dimension of intellectual capital is not just about the numbers; it reflects the company's acumen in efficient resource allocation, process optimization, and value creation (Otuya, Akpoyibo & Edike, 2023). Thus, capital employed efficiency is a strategic lever that companies can pull to achieve their broader financial objectives (Sonali & Kaushala, 2023). It embodies the intelligent allocation of resources, operational optimization, and value creation – all of which contribute to the enhancement of the firm's overall competitiveness and long-term sustainability.

Corporate Performance

Corporate performance pertains to the utilization of a company's resources within its core operations to generate revenue effectively (Sonali & Kaushala, 2023). Alternatively, it encompasses the achievement of specific business objectives, evaluated against predefined benchmarks, targets, and expenditures. Corporate performance reflects the degree to which a company attains its strategic goals and objectives with optimal resource employment (Uagbale-Ekatak & Ofurum, 2022). Corporate performance refers to the measure of the comprehensive competitiveness of an economic entity. It provides insights into the level of accomplishment regarding a firm's strategic aims (Habib & Dalwai, 2023). Corporate performance involves a holistic assessment of how effectively a firm executes its policies and operations to fulfill its predefined objectives (Gidado, Adedeji & Ali, 2023). This encompasses a quantifiable outcome that showcases the extent of goal attainment. Through a meticulously structured evaluation of corporate performance, managers gain the capability to assess the financial prosperity, health, and sustainability of the firm. This accentuates that the concept of corporate performance extends beyond it is mere face value, incorporating dimensions such as firm productivity, efficiency, effectiveness, and more, beyond the conventional focus on financial performance often found in corporate literature.

Empirical Review

Nguyen (2023) assessed how intellectual capital affected the financial performance of Vietnamese service sector companies between 2005 and 2014. The two-step system GMM model was used to analyze the data, which show that while structural capital efficiency had a variable impact on firm performance based on knowledge intensity levels and service activity types, human capital efficiency and capital employed efficiency had a positive effect. Chukwuekwu (2023) looked at how intellectual capital affected the expansion of companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. For this study, a sample size of ten publicly traded consumer goods companies spanning a ten-year period (2011–2020) was utilized. The impact of intellectual capital and its constituent parts on the sustainability and growth of businesses was examined through the application of regression analysis techniques. The analysis' findings showed that relational, structural, human, and physical capital all significantly positively influence the prediction of a company's ability to grow sustainably. The impact of intellectual capital on the financial performance and firm value of the Indonesian automobile sector was examined by Putri, Budiyanto, Triyonowati, and Ilham (2023). The study's population consisted of automobile businesses that were listed between 2014 and 2021 on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The study employed Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis to evaluate the hypothesis. The hypothesis test's findings demonstrated that intellectual capital significantly and favorably affects financial performance. Otuya, Akpoyibo, and Edike (2023) looked on the relationship between intellectual capital efficiency and wealth creation for shareholders in Nigeria between 2011 and 2022. The VAIC model was used in the study to evaluate intellectual capital, and regression analysis was conducted after descriptive statistics and diagnostic tests. The value added intellectual coefficient (VAIC), a measure of intellectual capital, and shareholders' wealth were found to be significantly positively correlated. The effect of intellectual capital on the enterprise value of listed

technical enterprises in Nigeria was determined by Abba, Hamidu, Kakanda, and Hanga (2023). A working population of seven out of nine firms was selected for the period spanning from 2012 to 2020. Correlation and multiple regression analysis were used to determine the study's conclusions, which show that intellectual capital has a significant and adverse effect on enterprise value. The level of intellectual capital efficiency in Nigeria's listed commercial banks and the variables affecting its efficient use were assessed by Olohunlana, Odeleye, and Isola in 2023. Based on yearly financial reports from 2013 to 2019, the study evaluates these banks' intellectual capital efficiency using data envelopment analysis (DEA). The study then uses Tobit regression to examine how firm-specific factors affect the efficiency of intellectual capital. The findings show that 91.67% of the Nigerian commercial banks evaluated are inefficient, and only 8.33% of them successfully optimize their intellectual capital. The impact of intellectual capital efficiency on the firm performance of the GCC industrial sector was investigated by Habib and Dalwai (2023). The information was taken from the Standard & Poor's database between 2015 and 2019. The findings show that most businesses do not make the best use of their investments in intellectual capital and that reform initiatives are required to reach best practices. The findings of the regression model show that the success of businesses is highly and favorably impacted by the efficiency of intellectual capital. The effect of intellectual capital (human capital, structural capital, and employed capital) on the financial performance of listed insurance businesses on the Amman Stock Exchange was investigated by Abuaddous, Albqour, and Salameh (2023). Twenty-one insurance businesses that were listed between 2011 and 2020 on the Jordanian Amman Stock Exchange make up the study population. The findings of the multiple regression analysis indicate that, in contrast to structural capital, human capital and capital employed have a considerable positive impact on return on equity. Sonali and Kaushala's (2023) study looked at how intellectual capital affected the performance of consumer staples firms in Colombia. Data were gathered for the panel data regression analysis using EViews, and the hypothesis was validated by looking at a sample of 25 Consumer Staple sector companies that were listed on the Colombo Stock Exchange between 2012 and 2020. This study discovered that, in the consumer staples industry, Human Capital and Capital Employed significantly improve business performance. Structural capital, however, has little effect on how well the company performs.

The impact of intellectual capital on the financial performance of banks listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange between 2019 and 2021 was examined by Misdar (2023). Secondary data from banking organizations' financial statements was used in this investigation. The study's hypotheses, which showed that relational, structural, and human capital all positively impact organizations' financial performance (FP), were tested using the linear regression test. Tonye and Oruh (2022) looked into how listed consumer companies in Nigeria fared financially from 2016 to 2020 in relation to the effectiveness of their intellectual capital. Regression study results demonstrated that both structural and human capital efficiency have a favorable and significant impact on economic value (ROA). On the other hand, capital employed efficiency has a detrimental and insignificant impact on Nigerian economic value. The impact of intellectual capital on the organizational performance of financial organizations listed in Nigeria was studied by Rufus, Festus, and Dada (2022). The Ex-Post Facto research design was used in the study. The data source was the external auditors' report on the audited financial

statements from 2010 to 2019. Regression analyses were utilized in conjunction with descriptive and inferential statistics. The study discovered that while capital employed efficiency has a significant positive impact on firm performance, human capital efficiency and structural capital efficiency had a non-significant beneficial impact on organizational performance.

Methodology

The research employs an ex-post facto research design, specifically utilizing the casual-comparative method. Ex-post facto research involves a study where the researcher works with independent variables that cannot be manipulated during the research process.

Population and Sample Size of the Study

The five agricultural companies quoted on the Nigerian Exchange Group make up the study's population. The study looked at these companies' ten-year annual reports and accounts from 2013 to 2022. The companies include Presco Plc, Ftn Cocoa Processors Plc, Okomu Oil Palm Plc, Ellah Lakes Plc, and Livestock Feeds Plc. For the sample size, the researcher used all five of the agricultural companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group.

Method of Data Collection

Secondary data from audited annual reports and accounts of the selected companies is used in the research. The Statement of Financial Position, the Statement of Profit or Loss, and the Comprehensive Income are where the data is taken from. This dataset covers the years 2013 through 2022, a total of ten years. Secondary data were used because they are approved by the Security and Exchange Commission (SEC), have the support of management, and are subject to external audit examination. Annual reports and accounts are respected and trustworthy sources.

Model Specification

The study adapted the model by Tonye and Oruh (2022)

$$EVA = a_0 + a_1 HCE_{it} + b_2 SCE_{it} + b_3 CEE_{it} + u$$

Where;

A0 = constant

EVA = Economic Value (ROA)

HCE = Human capital efficiency

SCE = Structural capital efficiency

CEE = Capital employed efficiency

The model above was modified to produce the specific model suitable for the study.

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 HCE_{it} + \beta_2 SCE_{it} + \beta_3 CEE_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots i$$

Where:

ROA is Return on Asset, calculated as earnings after-tax/total asset

HCE is Human Capital Efficiency, which is calculated as (Value Added)/(Human Capital)

SCE is Structural Capital Efficiency, which is calculated as (Structural Capital)/(Value Added)

CCE is Capital Employed Efficiency, which is calculated as (Value Added)/(Capital Employed)

β_{1-4} represents the regression coefficient;

ε represents the error term;

i represents individual firms and t represents the time/year.

Method of Data Analysis

The research's data analysis was conducted using information gathered from the Nigerian Exchange Group's publications and the cited companies' annual reports. Data from the Nigerian Exchange Group was used to compute the dependent and independent variables between 2013 and 2022.

The study variables' mean, median, standard deviation, kurtosis, and skewness are all summarized using descriptive statistics. Additionally, inferential statistics was applied using E-Views 9 in the following ways:

i. Coefficient of correlation: which is a good measure of relationship between two variables that tell us about the strength of relationship and the direction of the relationship as well?

ii. Multiple regressions analysis: Regression analysis predicts the value the dependent variable based on the value of the independent variable and explains the impact or effect of changes in the values of the variables.

Decision Rule

Accept the alternative hypothesis, if the Probability value (P-value) of the test is less than 0.05 (5%). Otherwise reject.

Data Analysis

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis

	ROA	HCE	SCE	CEE
Mean	0.079000	1.539000	0.318000	0.421000
Median	0.065000	1.510000	0.340000	0.440000
Maximum	0.250000	2.450000	0.590000	0.530000
Minimum	-0.030000	1.010000	0.010000	0.300000
Std. Dev.	0.075215	0.364104	0.146366	0.073594
Skewness	0.984521	1.184202	-0.358241	-0.498648
Kurtosis	3.404582	4.503522	3.325737	1.966017
Jarque-Bera	33.67346	65.58264	5.162101	17.19768
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.075694	0.000184
Sum	15.80000	307.8000	63.60000	84.20000
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.125800	26.38180	4.263200	1.077800
Observations	200	200	200	200

Source: E-View output, 2024

Interpretation of Descriptive Statistics

The return on assets of the sampled companies is 0.079, with a standard deviation of 0.075 and a maximum of 0.250, a minimum of -0.030, and descriptive data in Table 1. The collected observations yielded an average human capital efficiency (HCE) of 1.539, with a standard deviation of 0.364. The maximum observation was 2.450, while the smallest value was 1.010. With a maximum observation of 0.590 and a lowest value of 0.010, the structural capital efficiency (SCE) mean value was 0.318, with a standard deviation of 0.146. A minimum

value of 0.300 and a maximum observation of 0.530 are observed for the capital employed efficiency (CEE), which has an average of 0.421 and a standard deviation of 0.074.

The degree to which a random variable's probability distribution deviates from the normal distribution is measured by its skewness. According to Table 1, there is a positive skew in the probability distribution for ROE (0.000), HCE (0.000), SCE (0.076), and CEE (0.000).

Table 2: Pearson Correlation Matrix

	ROA	HCE	SCE	CEE
ROA	1			
HCE	0.738335	1		
SCE	0.606908	0.943270	1	
CEE	0.267081	0.256583	0.378995	1

Source: E-Views 9.0 Correlation Output, 2024

The Pearson Correlation Matrix in table 2 shows the existence of a positive relationship between HCE, SCE, CEE and ROA at a coefficient value of 0.738, 0.607 and 0.267.

Test of Hypotheses

Because the data included both time series (2013–2022) and cross-sectional characteristics (Nigerian agricultural firms), we used a pooled multiple regression analysis to investigate the impact relationships between the dependent variable debt and the independent variables (HCE, SCE, and CEE) as well as to test our formulated hypotheses. Table 3 below presents and discusses the findings of the multiple regression based on pooled interactions.

Table 3: OLS Regression Result

Dependent Variable: ROA

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 08/01/24 Time: 23:20

Sample: 2013 2022

Periods included: 10

Cross-sections included: 20

Total panel (balanced) observations: 200

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.394709	0.032762	-12.04761	0.0000
HCE	0.357543	0.027250	13.12088	0.0000
SCE	-0.575248	0.070800	-8.124986	0.0000
CEE	0.252682	0.048372	5.223771	0.0000
R-squared	0.664569	Mean dependent var		0.079000
Adjusted R-squared	0.659435	S.D. dependent var		0.075215
S.E. of regression	0.043894	Akaike info criterion		-3.394285
Sum squared resid	0.377629	Schwarz criterion		-3.328318
Log likelihood	343.4285	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-3.367589
F-statistic	129.4408	Durbin-Watson stat		1.966734
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: E-Views 9.0 Correlation Output, 2024

Interpretation of Regression Result

The adjusted Squared and R-squared values in Table 3 were 0.66 and 0.66, respectively. The results show that, taken together, the independent factors account for almost 66% of the systematic fluctuations in debt experienced by our sample firms over the course of 10 years (2013–2022). The modified R² value in Table 3 was 0.66. According to the corrected R², or coefficient of multiple determinations, the explanatory variables (HCE, SCE, and CEE) together account for 66% of the variation in the dependent variable (debt) of listed agricultural enterprises in Nigeria. The F-statistic value of 129.4408 with an associated Prob.>F = 0.000 indicates that the model is fit to explain the relationship expressed in the study model and further suggests that the explanatory variables are properly selected, combined, and used, so the adjusted R² of 66% did not constitute a problem for the study. The adjusted R² value of 94% indicates that additional factors not included in the study model account for 34% of the variation in the dependent variable.

Test of Autocorrelation: We further verify that our model is well-specified by utilizing the Durbin-Waston (DW) statistics, which we found using the regression result in table 3. The DW statistics is 1.966734. Additionally, the Akika Info Criterion and Schwarz Criterion, with respective values of -3.394285 and -3.328318, further support this finding. Along with the previously mentioned, the following are the particular conclusions drawn from each explanatory variable:

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Human capital efficiency does not significantly affect return on assets of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria

According to Table 3, the effectiveness of a company's human capital has a noteworthy beneficial impact on the return on assets of agricultural enterprises that are listed in Nigeria. This is evident from the highly statistically significant beta coefficient (β_1) of 0.357543 with a p-value of 0.000 at the 5% level of significance.

Decision

This study confirms that the human capital efficiency of the firm has a positive significant effect on return on assets of agricultural firms in Nigeria, as the test's P-value was 0.000 less than 0.05 (5%). Therefore, the alternative hypothesis is accepted and the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Structural capital efficiency does not significantly affect return on assets of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria.

Table 3 shows that the return on assets of listed agricultural enterprises in Nigeria is significantly positively impacted by the structural capital efficiency of the company. The aforementioned observation is supported by the highly statistically significant beta coefficient (β_1) of -0.575248 with a p-value of 0.000 at the 5% significance level.

This study confirms that the structural capital efficiency of the firm has a negative significant effect on return on assets of agricultural firms in Nigeria, with the P-value of the test being 0.000 less than 0.05 (5%). Therefore, the alternative hypothesis is accepted and the null hypothesis is rejected.

Hypothesis Three

H0₃: Capital employed efficiency does not significantly affect return on assets of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria.

Table 3 shows that the return on assets of listed agricultural enterprises in Nigeria is significantly positively impacted by the capital employed efficiency of the company. This is evident from the highly statistically significant beta coefficient (β_1) of 0.252682 with a p-value of 0.000 at the 5% level of significance.

This study confirms that capital employed efficiency of the firm has a positive significant effect on return on equity of agricultural firms in Nigeria, as the test's P-value was 0.000 less than 0.05 (5%). Therefore, the alternative hypothesis is accepted and the null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion

Using return on assets as the dependent variable and human capital efficiency, structural capital efficiency, and capital employed efficiency as the independent variables, the study assessed the impact of intellectual capital on the corporate performance of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria. The study design used in the research is ex post facto. The five (5) listed agricultural enterprises on the Nigerian Exchange Group make up the study's population. Companies that recognize the paramount importance of intellectual capital and strategically integrate it into their corporate strategies actively invest in developing and nurturing intellectual capital through employee training and development programs, fostering a knowledge-sharing culture, and promoting innovation and creativity.

The negative impact on ROA highlights the critical role of skilled, motivated, and well-managed human resources in the consumer goods sector. In an environment where innovation and adaptability are key, shortcomings in human capital management can lead to increased costs, reduced productivity, and ultimately, a diminished ROA. The negative effect on ROA underscores the importance of optimizing organizational structures, processes, and technologies. Firms that fail to adapt to evolving market dynamics and technological advancements may face increased operational costs, reduced competitiveness, and, consequently, a lower return on assets. The positive correlation with return on assets emphasizes the significance of prudent financial management and optimal capital allocation. Firms that strategically deploy their overall capital, balancing debt and equity, and investing in high-return projects, are more likely to experience higher profitability and, in turn, a positive impact on ROE. Therefore, addressing challenges in human capital and structural capital becomes integral to achieving sustained growth and profitability in the competitive agricultural sector.

Recommendations

1. Agricultural firm's should consider strategic investments in employee training and development, aiming to enhance overall productivity and consequently improve financial performance.
2. Managers of listed agricultural firms in Nigeria should prioritize streamlining processes, improving intellectual property management, and optimizing supply chain operations. By addressing these structural challenges, firms can work towards improving financial outcomes and maintaining a competitive edge in the market.

3. Recognizing the positive correlation between capital employed efficiency and ROA encourages agricultural firms in Nigeria to focus on optimizing asset utilization, managing debt levels prudently, and making strategic investment decisions to enhance overall financial performance.

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